

Impact of Musculoskeletal Pain on Health related Quality of Life (HRQoL) among Fishermen in Kano State (Nigeria)

Shittu Aishat^{ACDEF} Naziru Bashir Mukhtar^{DEF} Alao Habeeb^{ABEF}

Department of Physiotherapy, Faculty of Allied Health Sciences, Bayero University Kano (Nigeria).

Received: April 03.2016; Accepted: May 10.2016

Abstract

Introduction: Fishing is among the most dangerous occupations worldwide. Fishermen do exhaust their locomotor system and therefore; it is highly possible for them to have musculoskeletal pain (MSP) which may subsequently affect their quality of life. The aim of this study was to assess the impact of MSP on health related quality of life (HRQoL) among fishermen in Kano State (KS)

Materials and Methods: 124 subjects were recruited from the population of fishermen in KS in this cross sectional study using purposive sampling. Only participants that met the inclusion criteria were recruited, their Physical and anthropometric data were recorded. They completed self-administered questionnaire, NORDIC MSP assessment tool and EQ-5D questionnaire.

Results: The mean age and BMI of the participants were 31.5 ± 1.14 and 25.25 ± 6.47 respectively. Highest percentage of MSP was reported in 2-5 joints (58.9%) within the last 12 months and 48.4% within the last 7 seven days, however, there was little prevention in activities of daily living for the last 12 months with 70.4% having no pain. The EQ-5D

Questionnaire showed, there was more problem with pain dimension (78.23%) and least problem was reported in self-care dimension (17.74%), while the mean EQ-VAS score was 52.78 ± 15.28 . Finally, there was no significant relationship ($P > 0.05$) between the last 12 months, 7 days of present of MSP and last 12 months of MSP preventing usual activities and quality of life across all the domains of EQ-5D.

Conclusion: Fishermen present with MSP in varying parts of their body, however their MSP doesn't significantly affect their HRQoL.

Keywords: Fishermen, Musculoskeletal Pain, Health Related Quality of Life (HRQoL)

Introduction

Fishing is a particularly risky occupation associated with a lot of hazards; the working environment can be uncomfortable at many times [1]. Bad working environment characterized with rough surface, instability while standing on the boat, could predispose fishermen to various musculoskeletal disorders [2]. Their kind of activity is also associated with bad positioning usually attained while loading, unloading and setting the net which could involve squatting, sitting, kneeling or stooping most especially in an inappropriate position for long term [2, 3]. All these are risks that can lead to various kinds of musculoskeletal disorders and can predispose individuals working under this condition to pain [3].

Fishermen are also prone to various kinds of minor accidents and injuries that may be ignored; this can also pose them to musculoskeletal deficit [4]. Furthermore, straining or overloading the same groups of muscles (stooping, squatting, or kneeling), for a long period of time may leads to musculoskeletal problem [2]. Findings from studies [5, 6, 7] conducted in United State, Turkey and Norway, revealed that fishermen are exhausting their loco-motor system during the work, so it is highly

possible for them to have musculoskeletal system complaints.

Quality of life is an individual's perception of their position in life in the context of the culture and value systems in which they live and in relation to their goals, expectations, standards and concerns [8]. It is a broad ranging concept affected in a complex way by the person's physical health, psychological state, level of independence, social relationships, occupations and their relationships to salient features of their environment [8]. It is also a determinant on how someone accomplishes life goals [9]. Musculoskeletal pain resulting from exhaustion of locomotor system, straining and overuse, long term position in an inappropriate posture is no doubt a factor which can result to morbidity therefore affecting quality of living [7]. The state of being diseased may affect physical health, mental health, social functioning and general well being which are the theoretical framework of health-related quality of life, this may affect the efficiency of performance [10].

Living with morbidity that can hinder physical input can result to decrease productivity, thus lowering economic outcome thereby affecting the economic status of

the community and in turn the living standard of the community. This study therefore aimed at identifying the impact of musculoskeletal pain on health-related quality of life among fishermen in Kano State.

Materials and Methods

A cross-sectional research design was used and the study was delimited to fishermen with at least 1 year working experience, are working for a minimum of four times in a week and with one or more forms of Musculoskeletal Pain. Nordic musculoskeletal questionnaire (NMQ) was used as an assessment tool for musculoskeletal disorders in different body regions while Euroqol EQ-5d was used for health related quality of life

Four (4) Local Government Areas (LGAs) that had Rivers/Dams in Kano State were selected and 124 Fishermen were purposively recruited. An introductory letter from the Department of physiotherapy, Bayero University Kano, was taken to the Village Heads, through the District Heads of the respective LGAs and then delivered to heads of the fishermen in all the four (4) LGAs (Minjibir, Ajingi, Makoda and Karaye LGAs). An informed consent form was distributed to the various participants who met the inclusion criteria and agreed to take part in the study, they were duly signed. The procedure was explained to the fishermen who volunteered to participate.

The physical characteristic of height and weight were measured using the height and weight meters. The assessment of musculoskeletal pain and quality of life was done using NMQ and Euroqol EQ-5D: EuroQoL-5 Dimension Questionnaire (EQ-5D) respectively. Nordic musculoskeletal questionnaire: Have 3 dimensions that take the demographic risk factors and musculoskeletal symptoms, respondents were asked to tick in the appropriate boxes that correspond to their answers in the questionnaire. EQ-5D descriptive dimensions have 3 levels: no problems,

some problems, severe problems. The respondents were asked to indicate their health status by ticking in the box against the most appropriate statement in each of the 5 dimensions.

Two research assistants were used for the participants that need assistance. Completed questionnaires were retrieved from them individually and collectively at the site of administration (response rate was 100%).

Data Analysis procedure

Descriptive and inferential statistics were used for analyzing the data. Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation, frequency and percentage was used to describe the data. Inferential statistics of spearman rank correlation was used determine the relationship between musculoskeletal pain (in the last 12 months, 7days, and last 12months) and health related quality of life. Data were analysed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 16.0 and p-value was set at 0.05.

Results

A total number of 124 questionnaires were administered to the participants and all were obtained back. The mean age of the participants is 31.65±1.14 and their BMI is 25.25kg ± 6.47. (Table 1),

Table 1: Physical and Anthropometric Characteristics of Participants. Key: M=Mean, SD=Standard Deviation

Variables	M±SD
Age	31.65 ± 1.14
BMI	25.25 ± 6.47

The Nordic musculoskeletal assessment shows that higher proportion of the participants have musculoskeletal pain in more than one joint, between 2-5 joints. In the last 12 months, the percentage was 58.4%, and in the last 7days is 48.4%. Joint pain has limited effect on their normal activities in the last 12 months (12.8%) (Table 2).

Table 2: Nordic Musculoskeletal Assessment during the last 12 month, Prevention from Normal Activities and in the Last 7 days

Nordic Musculoskeletal Assessment during the last 12 month		
Joints	Frequency	(%)
Non	11	8.8
One joint	12	9.6
2-5 joints	73	58.4
More than 5 joint	26	20.8
Total	124	100
Prevention from carrying out normal activities in the last 12 months		
Non	88	70.4
One joint	19	15.2
2-5 joints	16	12.8
More than 5 joints	1	1.6
Total	124	100
Nordic musculoskeletal assessment during the last 7days		
No joint	45	36.3
One joint	5	4.0
2-5 joints	60	48.4
More than 5 joint	12	9.7

In table 3, pain problem has the highest percentage of 78.23% among the 5 dimensions of EQ-5D across the age groups. Problem with mobility is ranked second with 58.87%, while self care has the least with 17.74%. (Table 3).

Table 3: The status of EQ-5D quality of life assessment

EQ_5D Dimension	Age group		Total N (%)
	15-40 N (%)	41-67 N (%)	
Mobility			
No problem	42 33.87	9 7.2	51 (41.13)
Problem	62 50	11 8.87	73(58.87)
Self care			
No problem	85 68.55	17 13.71	102(82.26)
Problem	19 15.32	3 2.42	22(17.74)
Usual activity			
No problem	79 63.71	13 10.48	92(74.19)
Problem	25 20.16	7 5.65	32(25.80)
Pain			
No problem	23 18.55	4 3.23	27(21.77)
Problem	81 65.32	16 12.90	97(78.23)
Depression			
No problem	43 38.71	19 9.00	52(41.94)
Problem	61 49.19	11 8.87	72(58.06)

Table 4 shows the participants perceived health status with majority scoring above 50 on the euroqol_vas. (Table 4).

Table 4: Euroqol_VAS Quality of Life Assessment

EQ_VAS Score	Age group		Total
	15-40yrs	41-67yrs	
30	7	0	7
40	28	7	35
45	11	1	12
50	17	5	22
55	5	1	6
60	12	3	15
65	4	0	4
70	10	1	11
75	1	0	1
80	3	0	3
90	6	2	8

Table 5, shows that there is no significant ($p>0.05$) relationship between musculoskeletal pain and health related quality of life across the domains within the last 12 months, within the last 7 days and with respect to activity prevention (Table 5, 6)

Table 5: Relationship between Nordic and EQ-5D scores in last 12 months and last 7 days

Domain	Last 12 days		Last 7 days	
	R	p	R	p
Mobility	-0.71	0.44	0.05	0.63
Self care	-0.85	0.35	-0.13	0.19
Usual activity	-0.06	0.52	0.31	0.76
Pain/Discomfort	-0.03	0.74	0.51	0.62
Depression	-0.05	0.57	0.08	0.46

Table 6: Relationship between Nordic scores and EQ-5D scores in last 12 months activities prevention

Domain	r	P value
Mobility	-0.11	0.22
Self care	-0.01	0.92
Usual	-0.10	0.25
Pain/discomfort	-0.02	0.82
Depression	-0.13	0.16

Discussion:

The impact of musculoskeletal pain on health related quality of life was investigated among fishermen in Kano. A total of 124 fishermen participated in the study. The dominant age range was within 15-40 years. The outcome of this study showed that majority of the fishermen had musculoskeletal pain across the region of the body parts with highest affectation between 2-5 joints with little impact on activities of daily living. This could be explained by the nature of work which is repetitive, as a result of the use of continuous and manually operated canoes and the use of calabash as compared to use of machinery which could help in the reduction of the impacts of repetitive force used on the body parts. This is in line with a similar study [11] that concluded that there were various occupational hazards among fishermen and musculoskeletal pain is the most prevalent.

The findings of the study revealed that most of the participants have problem with mobility, pain/discomfort and depression domains in the euroqol health related quality of life questionnaire (EQ-5D) than the other domains (self care, usual activities) this was in agreement with the previous studies [12] which stated that physical

health problems and bodily pain were the most affected by the presence of MSD and another study [13] which stated that Intensity of the pain, functional disability and number of locations with musculoskeletal pain were found to have a detrimental impact on the physical health of the workers and that depressive syndrome and greater functional disability due to back pain, in turn, predict worse mental health. Also, the EQ-5D VAS score which assess the perceived health status at that particular time revealed that majority of the participant score above average. This could imply that the MSP experienced by the workers do not significantly affect their wellbeing.

This study also shows that there was no significant relationship between the musculoskeletal pain and health related quality of life among fishermen in the last twelve (12) months, in the last seven (7) days and in the prevention of activities within the last twelve (12) month. This was contrary to a study conducted [14] which revealed a worse health related quality of life in people with musculoskeletal diseases than in the general population, typically in the areas of pain, physical functioning or mobility, role limitation due to physical health problems, and usual activities. This could further be attributed to the fact that the study population was high compared to this work and the population was on general populace. Probably because they established a specific diagnosed musculoskeletal condition and use of a different questionnaires. Furthermore, possible explanations for this could be that either musculoskeletal pain is considered a minor symptom, or the study population (fishermen) were able to perform their usual activities, even when experiencing musculoskeletal pain. This could also be attributed to the fact that the population studied believed that once they get in water all their pain will disappear and it's normal with the nature of the occupation coupled with the use of local herbs. This is supported by [15] who in his study explained that believe can strongly influence the impact of MSD on quality of life than pain intensity.

The study also shows that the populations do not seek medical care. This is in agreement with the study of [12] which stated that it is apparent from our study that most people with musculoskeletal pain do not seek care from primary care services. In general, factors influencing consultation include patients' demographics, health beliefs and expectations, social status, accessibility to health care, functional status and co-morbidity [16].

Conclusion:

From the findings of this study it is therefore concluded that, though fishermen present with MSP in varying parts of their body, their MSP doesn't significantly affect their HRQoL (Table 2).

References:

1. Frantzeskou E., Kastania AN., Riza E., Jensen OC., Linos A. Risk factors for fishermen's health and safety in Greece. *International Maritime Health*, 2012; 63(3), 155-61.
2. Hignett S., McAtamney L. 'Rapid entire body assessment (RE-BA)', *Applied Ergonomics*, 2000; 31, p. 201-205.
3. Kristen L., Kucera A., McDonald MA. Occupational stressors identified by small-scale, independent commercial crab pot fishermen; Duke Center for Community Research, Division of Community Health, Duke University, Durham, 2010; NC, USA. 672-679.
4. Matheson C., Morrison S., Murphy E., Lawrie T., Ritchie L., Bond C. The health of fishermen in the catching sector of the fishing industry: a gap analysis. *Occup Med* 2001; 51: 305-311.
5. Dotter E. 'Winter harvest of danger: fishing on board a Maine trawler in the storm-tossed North Atlantic'. *Public Health Rep* 2002; 117(4):324-30.
6. Tander B., Canbaz S., Canturk F., Peksen Y. Work-related musculoskeletal problems among pharmaceutical sales representatives in Samsun, Turkey. *Journal of Back and Musculoskeletal Rehabilitation* 2007; 20(1):21-27. 30.
7. Kucera KL., Loomis D., Lipscomb HJ., Marshall SW., Mirka GA., Daniels JL. Ergonomic risk factors for low back pain in North Carolina crab pot and gill net commercial fishermen'. *Am J Ind Med* 2009; 52(4):311-21.
8. Measuring quality of life the World Health Organization quality of life instruments (1997) who/msa/mnh/psf/97.4
9. Ioana S. The quality of life and rural development in meseş area. Doctoral Thesis Summary. Cluj-Napoca 2012;
10. Tüzün EH. Quality of life in chronic musculoskeletal pain. *Best Pract Res Clin Rheumatol* 2007; 21:567-579.
11. El-Saadawy ME., Soliman NE., El-Tayeb IMM., Hammouda MA. Some occupational health hazards among fishermen in Alexandria city. *Gaziantep Med J* 2014; 20(1):71-78
12. Antonopoulou M., Antonakis N., Hadjipavlou A., Lionis C. 'Studying the association between musculoskeletal disorders, quality of life and mental health. A primary care pilot study in rural Crete, Greece' *Fam Pract*, 2009; 10:143
13. Rodrigues DE., Kiran U. A pilot study on knowledge & practice regarding prevention of occupational hazards and attitude towards utilization of safety measures among fishermen working at a selected harbor. *Nitte University Journal of Health Science* 2013; 3(3):68-71.
14. Picavet HSJ. National health interview surveys by mail or home interview: effects on response. *J Epidemiol Community Health* 2001; 55:408-13
15. Lame IE., Madelon LP., Johan WS., Maarten V., Patijn JK. 'Quality of life in chronic pain is more associated with beliefs about pain, than with pain intensity' *European Journal of Pain* 9, 2005; 15-24.
16. Bedson J., Mottram S., Thomas E., Peat G. 'Knee pain and osteoarthritis in the general population: what influences patients to consult' *Fam Pract* 2007; 24:443-453.

Correspondence address

Shittu Aishat
Department of Physiotherapy,
Bayero University Kano, Nigeria
+2348036785233,
Email: abdulzeezaisha@gmail.com

Conflict of interest:

The authors have declared no conflict of interest.